

Nanochain of BiFeO₃ and Bi₂Fe₄O₉ Prepared by hydrothermal method and study of their magnetic properties

Aditi Sahoo, Dipten Bhattacharya*

CSIR-Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute,
196, Raja S.C. Mullick Road, Kolkata- 700032, India
E-mail: dipten@cgcric.res.in

Abstract:

Synthesis of self-assembled magnetic nanochains is found to be very promising because of their distinctive optical, electrochemical and magnetic properties. They can be used in microchemical sensor, magnetic switching, DNA separation etc. Here 18-carbon chain fatty-acid is used as surfactant. We have synthesized BiFeO₃ and Bi₂Fe₄O₉ nanochains. The morphology, chemical composition, phase purity and crystal structure of the as-prepared samples were determined by TEM, EDX and XRD respectively. The nano chains are composed of spherical particles of size 20-30 nm. Length of the nanochains varies from few tens of nanometres to even few micrometres. We have measured the room temperature magnetic properties such as magnetization at 1.5 Tesla, remnant magnetic moment, coercivity etc. We have noticed differences in the magnetic properties between those of isolated nanoparticles and their self-assembled patterns. The results appear to be promising for tuning the multiferroic properties by tailoring different self-assembled patterns of the nanoscale particles.

Keywords: Multiferroics, Self-assembly, Enhance-magnetization

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